

Fig. 2. Fog Computing enabled Multi-Cloud Architecture

MOTIVATION

The primary objective of this work is to improve real-time data analysis by utilizing fog computing to optimize IoT integration in multi-clouds to minimize latency. IoT devices can exchange data, including those from smart cities, healthcare systems, and any existing communication scenario. Due to COVID-19, online communication and cloud usage are continuously increasing. The cloud could be overburdened, and latency might be a problem due to the massive volume of data from heterogeneous IoT devices. Improving the performance and latency of IoT nodes and the scalability and stability of IoT networks is complicated, scattered contexts are the primary motivations for the optimal integration of IoT in multi-cloud environments through fog computing.

CONTRIBUTION

The main contributions are given below:

- Design and develop a proposed architecture for optimized integration of IoT in multi-clouds through fog computing to reduce latency in communication.
- Analyze the existing communication protocols of the Internet and IoT devices.
- Comparative analysis of lightweight protocols with different lengths of messages.
- Furthermore, it analyzes a comparative study of multiple jobs created per second by IoT devices using a proposed architecture.

Overall, contribution should aim to advance the state-of-the-art in fog computing optimization, addressing key challenges and paving the way for more efficient and effective integration of fog computing in various applications.

STRUCTURE OF THE PAPER

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. [Section 2](#) provides a background and state of the art about optimized integration of IoT in multi-cloud through fog computing. [Section 3](#) and [Section 4](#) provide the problem formulation and the system overview of our proposed work, a fog computing real-time data analytics integrating IoT devices over the cloud in detail. The [Section 5](#) provide the evaluation based on the performance and then the [last section](#) provides the conclusion and future directions.

RELATED WORK

The goal of task allocation job optimization is to minimize latency and bandwidth consumption, as discussed in [6]. Using an AI technique, the work examines energy, latency, and network utilization using a video surveillance system. The energy-based task distribution across multi-cloud networks lowers total energy consumption, as introduced in [7]. By allocating the random technique, such as cloud Z-score normalization (CZSN) and fuzzy resource utilization (FR-MOS), the energy usage is improved up to 14.6%, 6.43%, and 2.18% by applying the proposed model. The inter-fog load balancing problem is the primary concern of [8], which aims to lower the computational expenses of communication and processing stress in the fog network coupled with NB-IoT wireless

technology. As an outcome, they proposed an architecture for distributive and strategic time scheduling based on bankruptcy games, which is perfect for collecting data from NB-IoT devices in a fog computing network [9-11]. Unlike the conventional mechanism, the suggested Shapley value-based technique may rationally arrange the limited temporal resources that the NB-IoT carrier offers to the NB-IoT devices. Shi et al. [12] fog and software-defined networking (SDN) architectures are suggested as ways to reduce latency in cloud-based mobile facial recognition systems. The authors also described fog/cloud load balancing and software-defined networking (SDN) as optimization issues. As a potential remedy for this issue, they suggested using a firework algorithm (FWA) based on SDN-centralized control within a wireless sensor network and fog environment coupled with microgrids. The scheduling issue in cloud computing merging the GELS and GA algorithms is presented in [13]. In a, the suggested approach (GAGELS) improves efficiency in finding the optimal solution by fusing the local search capacity of GELS with the GA. The effectiveness of the suggested algorithm is assessed by contrasting its outcomes with those of the PSO and GA algorithms. The results of the trial show that GAGELS performs better and is very effective at resolving work scheduling challenges. Furthermore, GAGELS outperforms the GA and PSO algorithms by 10% and 30%, respectively, but at the expense of increased execution time. It is possible to evaluate the relationship between GA and other LSAs in order to speed up the proposed algorithm's execution. Future work may look into the impact of different GA settings on the caliber of the outcomes. Lawal et al. [14] presents the analysis of energy consumption. It shows that fog computing can be more effective when core services are optimized for energy usage. As an illustration, consider the findings of the CCTV energy consumption scalability research, which showed that, at 20 devices, fog computing had a little greater energy consumption than cloud computing—in contrast to cloud computing, fog computing energy usage levels dropped consistently from 40 to 200 devices. When it came to CO₂, the energy consumption of the fog computing system was higher than that of the cloud for the first 40 devices, but then it started to decrease as there were 200 devices. The data from the light sensors show a different pattern: at 20 devices, fog computing energy levels are lower than cloud computing levels, but they rise to become more significant at 40 devices, and then they gradually decline from 60 to 200 devices. Awasthi et al. [15] According to studies, there are difficulties in protecting sensitive data in Internet of Things environments. However, blockchain technology can enable safe data sharing between different systems. TD plus Bs (28) = Rp ARR (> 96%), DPI (highest degree), computational overhead (7 m), and storage overheads (13 MB) are just a few of the metrics that indicate that the M-BSF framework—which combines edge-level, fog-level, and cloud-level security via baby kyber and scaling cyber cryptosystems with reliable hashing techniques in blockchain—is a good substitute for the approaches used today. It is also observed that the suggested framework for tackling several common threats at edge, fog, and cloud levels yields higher tractability among users. Decentralized identification systems will be integrated to improve user privacy and control over their data in IoT environments. The suggested M-BSF security architecture offers a viable method of protecting sensitive data in IoT settings. In [16], Abedin et al. aim to reduce the computational costs of communication and computing strains in the fog network equipped with NB-IoT wireless technology [17] and primarily focus on the inter-fog load balancing problem. They consequently suggested a bankruptcy game architecture for distributive and strategic time scheduling, which is ideal for gathering data from NB-IoT devices in a fog computing network. The suggested Shapley value-based technique, in contrast to traditional methods, may reasonably plan for the limited temporal resources that the NB-IoT carrier provides to the NB-IoT devices. In [18], Misirli et al.'s investigation of the task scheduling context in fog computing reveals a noteworthy evolution characterized by significant growth and game-changing adjustments. They obtained insights into the challenges, remedies, and potential applications of task scheduling in fog computing by conducting. The constant quest for efficiency, which includes resource allocation, low-latency delivery, energy consumption, and cost-effectiveness, is at the core of fog task scheduling. The examination emphasizes review highlights several significant research gaps that indicate an urgent need for more research. How dynamic this subject is and how continuous efforts are made to improve scheduling procedures. Notably, the review highlights several significant research gaps that indicate an urgent need for more research. These gaps include investigating AI-driven scheduling through understandable machine learning techniques, creating novel autonomous task scheduling algorithms, and the examination of mobility-aware, availability-aware, and multi-criteria task scheduling. These significant findings highlight the necessity of ongoing progress in fog computing [20] task scheduling in order to fully realize its potential in a variety of domains. Fog computing is used in this work to introduce optimized IoT integration in multi-cloud environments.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

Integrating a multi-cloud fog layer with IoT devices can be highly profitable in several fields. IoT gathers data from sensors connected to multiple and heterogeneous things, allowing the Cloud to connect IoTs through the fog layer. The end user at the IoT layer requires the required level of service; hence, task scheduling in the fog is essential. The QoS standard considers four consumption factors for integrating multiple cloud-fog-IoT layers with devices to maximize bandwidth, latency, robustness, time, cost, and power. Due to the massive data generation of IoT device storage, access from the Cloud is a major problem. Communication between IoT nodes to Cloud and multi-cloud latency is also a major issue. In this work, we have addressed the integration of IoT devices with multi-fog and cloud environments using MQTT, HTTP, and other lightweight protocols via communication delay to reduce latency.

PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

This section presents a proposed architecture, which is a multi-layered architecture for IoT node integration through fog layer nodes. The three tiers consist of L_1 , L_2 , and L_3 layers: IoT/edge layer, fog layer, and cloud layer. Fog computing is mainly a virtualization technology that offers storage and computing between end devices and the cloud layer as an interface between the lower and higher layers. The schematic overview of our proposed architecture is shown in Fig. 3. The first L_1 layer is the physical layer or IoT device layer or edge layer, composed of IoT devices and hardware components with specific functions that transmit data over networks, including the internet, such as sensors, actuators, gadgets, appliances, or machines. These gadgets might make use of various communication protocols [18]. The core job of the sensors at the L_1 layer is to collect all data and send it to edge-fog gateways. Then, the second tier will consist of edge gateways and edge-fog servers. When data arrives at edge gateways, the data needs to be filtered out and pre-processed for further processing. Communication between the L_1 and L_2 layers uses different communication technologies and protocols. Through this, it is possible to reduce the data transmission burden and increase the data analysis processing speed. This tier works as a server. The amount of data arrives at fog servers and is then distributed among the various IoT devices, and maybe at cloud layer devices, according to the computation requirements of the data to reduce the latency in real-time scenarios. The offloading of requests must be done using a proposed efficient task-scheduling algorithm. However, we have considered, by default, scheduling in this study. The second L_2 layer is fog layer. Fog computing facilitates preprocessing data before reaching the cloud, minimizing communication time and reducing the need for substantial volumes of data storage via filtering. This layer consists of fog access, a cloud-fog gateway, and fog storage.

Fog Access: At the periphery of a fog computing network, a fog access point (FAP) is a networking device that offers services and connectivity. By bringing cloud computing closer to data generation and consumption points on the network edge, fog computing expands its possibilities. Because they act as the point of entry for devices to join the fog network, FAPs are essential to the functionality of this architecture.

Cloud fog gateway: A networking device or software element that connects cloud and fog computing resources is called a Cloud Fog Gateway (CFG). It serves as a bridge that links cloud servers housed in centralized data centers to fog nodes situated at the network's edge. Enabling smooth communication and data exchange across fog and cloud settings is CFG's primary goal.

Fog Storage: Fog storage refers to storing data and resources at the edge of the network in a fog computing environment. Fog computing extends the capabilities of cloud computing to the edge of the network, closer to where data is generated and consumed. Fog storage plays a crucial role in enabling applications that require low latency, real-time data processing, security, and efficient use of network bandwidth [19].

Fig. 3. Proposed Multi Layered Architecture

The third L_3 layer is the cloud layer. The cloud layer is the basic architecture that improves the computation of tasks in IoT integration, such as Amazon AWS, Microsoft Azure, IBM, and so on. This is the topmost layer of our proposed architecture. This layer consists of real-time data processing, secure storage as an Interplanetary File System (IPFS) [20], [21] and data centres.

Servers: Servers can be physical machines or virtualized instances running on cloud infrastructure. They can also be categorized based on their function, such as web servers, database servers, application servers, and file servers, each serving a specific purpose in a computing environment. **Storage:** Digital data is kept in a data storage device through computer technology. IPFS is another option for a secure storage system. This method can temporarily or permanently store data on a computer [21].

Virtual Machine: A software-based simulation of a physical computer is called a virtual machine (VM). It allows you to run multiple operating systems (OS) concurrently on a single physical machine. With virtualization technology, you may create and operate a virtualized environment that functions similarly to a different physical computer. Each virtualized environment has its own virtual hardware, such as memory, CPU, storage, and network interfaces.

Storage: Virtual machine (VM) storage must be adequately managed and safeguarded to avoid data loss and guarantee peak performance, regardless of the storage technology employed. This includes putting backup and disaster recovery plans into action, keeping an eye on how much storage is being used, and routinely optimizing storage configurations [20].

Data Center(s): Businesses utilize data centers as physical repositories for storing vital applications and information. Switches, servers, firewalls, routers, and storage systems are the main elements of a data center architecture. Data centers may also employ storage virtualization and these technologies to abstract physical storage resources and offer a more adaptable and scalable storage infrastructure. Storage virtualization can increase storage efficiency and make managing storage resources easier [21].

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we evaluate the performance optimization integration of IoT in multi-cloud using fog computing. In the simulation, Cloudsim 5.0 [22] and [23] are employed to simulate multi-cloud and fog computing in the simulation environment for IoT devices. The experiment is run on Cloudsim to analyze the optimized integration of IoT devices in terms of message delay in the HTTP and MQTT protocols with multi-cloud via fog and multi-fog with 3000 MIPS processing speed, a virtual machine of 40000 MB with 4096 MB of memory and 6000 MB of bandwidth, and a Windows operating system. The analysis is presented in the paper in the subsequent subsection. The following sections of this work address the specifics of the analysis of the lightweight communication protocol of IoT, along with comparative analyses over fog and multi-cloud. Table 1 shows the parameters used in the simulation.

Table 1. Simulation Parameters.

Simulation Parameters used in CloudSim		
S. No.	Parameters	Values
1	System Type	X86
2	Operating System	Windows
3	Time Zone(Resources)	10.0
4	Size of VM	1000
5	Processing Cost	3.0
6	Memory	0.05
7	Storage Cost	0.1
8	Bandwidth Cost	0.1
Simulation Parameters used in Virtual Machine		
1	Number of Host	1
2	Processing Speed (MIPS)	2000
3	Memory(MB)	2048
4	Bandwidth	3000
5	PesNumber	1
6	Size of VM	1000
Simulation Parameters used in Cloudlet		
1	Cloudlet Length	20000
2	File Size	500
3	Output Size	500
4	Size of VM	1000

ANALYSIS OF LIGHTWEIGHT COMMUNICATION AMONG IOT TO FOG

Fig. 4 shows communication among IoT nodes to the Fog layer node. It has been observed that the MQTT layer for IoT devices performs lightweight communication in terms of communication delay. The communication delay is exponentially increasing as the devices increase. In addition, the result shows that the delay at 50 IoT nodes over a single fog is 0.5 ms. more from the HTTP layer. The size of the job or packet of the IoT node is considered to be 100 bits, and Cloudsim provides the allocation of messages from IoT nodes at the Fog layer node based on first come, first served (FCFS).

Fig. 4. Computational delay analysis of IoT nodes between node(s) at Fog layer.

We have also analyzed other communication protocols of IoT nodes at the fog layer. Fig. 5 illustrates that CoAP is most suitable for IoT device communication after the MQTT protocol. However, the AMQP protocol has the highest delay of up to 4 ms. In the fog layer, delay-decreased proximity to IoT devices reduces data travel time, leading to quicker processing and lower latency; delay-increased limited computational resources can cause bottlenecks, leading to higher delays during peak load times. In the IoT layer, delay decreases efficient routing, and optimized network paths enhance data transmission speed, reducing overall delay; network congestion and poor bandwidth can slow down data transfer, increasing the delay.

Fig. 5. Computational delay analysis of IoT nodes using different lightweight protocols with node(s) at Fog layer.

Fig. 6 shows the analysis of IoT devices over multi-fog communication using FCFS. The result also compares the communication delays of optimized integration of IoT nodes over single-fog and multi-fog using a lightweight communication protocol.

Fig. 6. Computational delay analysis of IoT nodes between node(s) at Fog/ Multi-fog layer.

ANALYSIS OF LIGHTWEIGHT COMMUNICATION AMONG IOT TO CLOUD

Fig. 7 shows communication among IoT nodes to the Cloud layer node. It has been observed that the MQTT layer for IoT devices performs lightweight communication in terms of communication delay. The communication delay is exponentially increasing as the devices increase. To evaluate the efficacy of the proposed model, we have also analysed the comparison of MQTT with HTTP in direct fog and cloud communication for IoT integration, respectively. In this result, IoT devices integrated at the edge layer directly communicate with fog nodes at the fog layer or middle layer and directly between servers or nodes at the cloud layer. The results show that ten nodes delays are doubled using MQTT up to 0.23 ms. However, the communication delay is 3.6 times greater when using HTTP. In addition, communication by 50 IoT nodes to the node at the fog layer and cloud layer delays are 3.2 and 4.1 by MQTT and 3.7 and 4.2 ms by HTTP, respectively.

Fig. 7. Computational delay analysis of IoT nodes between node(s) at Cloud layer.

Fig. 8 shows the analysis of IoT devices over multi-cloud communication using FCFS. The result also compares the communication delays of optimized integration of IoT nodes over single-cloud and multi-cloud using a lightweight communication protocol, MQTT and HTTP. The result proves that when 50 nodes directly communicating with single cloud and multi-cloud, the delays are 4.12 and 3.8 using MQTT; similarly, delays are 4.2 and 3.95 ms using HTTP, respectively. If all 500 IoT devices communicate with single cloud and multi-cloud by MQTT and HTTP, then delays are 17.12, 16.82, 17.41, and 17.24 ms, respectively.

Fig. 8. Computational delay analysis of IoT nodes between node(s) at Cloud/Multi-cloud.

ANALYSIS OF LIGHTWEIGHT COMMUNICATION AMONG IOT TO CLOUD THROUGH FOG LAYER

Fig. 9 shows communication among IoT nodes to the Cloud layer node through the Fog layer. We have considered 500 IoT devices communicating at the Cloud layer via the Fog layer, and each IoT node is producing one job at a time. The communication delays of 500 IoT nodes are 17.0 and 16.89 ms using HTTP and MQTT protocols, respectively.

Fig. 9. Computational delay of IoT devices between node(s) at Cloud layer through Fog layer at one job per IoT device.

We have also analyzed the same scenario when each IoT node produces 10 jobs simultaneously per *ms*. The communication delays are depicted in Fig. 10. The job size 1000 bits is assumed. The result shows that delay is reduced because of the fog node assigning jobs to the cloud as per default scheduling in the operating system, and the cloud is also increasing capacity as per requirement. The communication delays of 500 IoT nodes are 6.8 and 6.7 ms using HTTP and MQTT protocols, respectively. However, at 100 IoT nodes, over ten jobs delay is just half up to 3.4 and 3.3, respectively, using HTTP and MQTT protocol.

Fig. 10. Computational delay of IoT devices between node(s) at Cloud layer through Fog layer at ten job per IoT device.

ANALYSIS OF LIGHTWEIGHT COMMUNICATION AMONG IOT NODES TO CLOUD/MULTI-CLOUD THROUGH FOG/MULTI-FOG

All IoT devices communicate with the cloud through fog nodes in this scenario. Fig. 11 shows that when using MQTT at 50 and 70 IoT nodes, communication delays are less in the order of 0.6 and 0.8 ms, respectively. However, when 100 IoT devices communicate with the cloud through the fog layer, a delay of 0.25 ms is high compared to the HTTP protocol.

Fig. 11. Computational delay analysis of IoT nodes using different protocols at Cloud layer through Fog Layer.

When comparing HTTP and MQTT, it was observed that the latter exhibits longer communication latency. This is because MQTT is a lightweight messaging protocol that is well-suited for IoT devices due to its low bandwidth usage, low power consumption, and efficient handling of intermittent connections. One of the reasons MQTT can have a lower communication delay compared to HTTP is because MQTT processes data bitwise or in parallel, whereas HTTP processes data character-wise.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The work studied an IoT integration over a multi-cloud with a fog layer to reduce latency. Delay quality used on CloudSim successfully achieved overall analysis performance. Through the proposed architecture, it was found that the MQTT protocols function best for IoT devices. A comparative analysis of latency utilizing the MQTT with other protocols demonstrated performance evaluation at various IoT nodes and bit counts. The work was further

improved by utilizing other protocols, such as AMQP and COAP, to obtain optimal load balancing and successful results in fog computing. In the future, IoT integration will also assess energy, investigate natural optimisation methods, and reduce network latency.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The work is not submitted to any other journal. There is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Hajvali M, Adabi S, Rezaee A., Hosseinzadeh M. Decentralized and scalable hybrid scheduling-clustering method for real-time applications in volatile and dynamic Fog-Cloud Environments. *Journal of Cloud Computing*. 2023; 12(66): 1-35; <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13677-023-00428-4>
2. Connected IoT Devices by 2030, Online available at: <http://www.rsc.org/dose/title> of subordinate document. Accessed 23 April 2024.
3. Tripathi G, Singh VK, Chaurasia BK. An energy-efficient heterogeneous data gathering for sensor-based internet of things. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*. 2023; 82: 42593–42616; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-15161-y>
4. Adhikari M, Hazra A, Menon VG, Chaurasia BK, Mumtaz S. A Roadmap of Next-Generation Wireless Technology for 6G-enabled Vehicular Networks. In *IEEE Internet of Things Magazine*. 2021; 4(4): 79-85; <https://doi.org/10.1109/IOTM.001.2100075>
5. Atzori L, Iera A, Morabito G. The Internet of Things: A survey. *Computer Networks*. 2010; 54(15): 2787–2805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2010.05.010>
6. Aljuhani A, Alhubaishy A. Dynamic Cloud Resource Allocation: A Broker-Based Multi-Criteria Approach for Optimal Task Assignment. *Applied Sciences*. 2024; 14(302): 1-17; <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14010302>
7. Singh Y, Kandah F, Zhang W. A secured cost-effective multi-cloud storage in cloud computing. In *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Commun. Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*, 2011, 619–624. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INFCOMW.2011.5928887>
8. Das R, Inuwa MM. A review on Fog Computing: Issues, Characteristics, Challenges, and Potential Applications. *Telematics and Informatics Reports*. 2023; 10(100049): 1-20; <https://doi.org/10.100049.10.1016/j.teler.2023.100049>
9. Muneeb M, Ko K-M, Park Y-H. A Fog Computing Architecture with Multi-Layer for Computing-Intensive IoT Applications. *Appl. Sci*. 2021; 11(11585): 1-11; <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112411585>
10. Mishra SK, Mishra S, Alsayat A, Jhanjhi NZ, Humayun M, Sahoo KS, Luhach AK. Energy-aware task allocation for multi-cloud networks. In *IEEE Access* 2020; 8: 178825–178834; <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3026875>
11. Abedin SK, Bairagi AK, Munir MS, Tran NH, Hong CH. Fog Load Balancing for Massive Machine Type Communications: A Game and Transport Theoretic Approach. In *IEEE Access* 2018; 6:1-16; <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2888869>
12. Shi C, Ren Z, He X. Research on load balancing for software defined cloud-fog network in real-time mobile face recognition, in *Communications and Networking*. In *ICST Institute for Computer Sciences, Social Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering* 2018, . https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66628-0_12.
13. Praveen SP, Ghasempoor H, Shahabi N, Izanloo F. A Hybrid Gravitational Emulation Local Search-Based Algorithm for Task Scheduling in Cloud Computing. *Hindawi Mathematical Problems in Engineering* 2023; 6516482: 1-9; <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/6516482>
14. Lawal KN, Olaniyi TK, Gibson RM. Leveraging Real-World Data from IoT Devices in a Fog–Cloud Architecture for Resource Optimisation within a Smart Building. *Appl. Sci*. 2024; 14(316): 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14010316>
15. Awasthi C, Mishra KP, Pal KP, Khan BS, Agarwal KA, Gadekallu RT, Malibari AA. Preservation of Sensitive Data Using MultiLevel Blockchainbased Secured Framework for Edge Network Devices. *J Grid Computing* 2023; 21(69): 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10723-023-09699-2>
16. Abedin SF, Bairagi AK, Munir MS, Tran NH, Hong CS. Fog load balancing for massive machine type communications: A game and transport theoretic approach. *IEEE Access* 2019; 7: 4204–4218. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2888869>.
17. Tripathi S, Chaurasia BK. Lightweight Communication in IoT using MQTT, *IEEE ISKCON*. 2023; 1-6; <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCON57294.2023.10112105>
18. Misirli J., Casalicchio E. An Analysis of Methods and Metrics for Task Scheduling in Fog Computing. *Future Internet* 2024; 16(16), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi16010016>.
19. Pandey U, Srivastav VK, Chaurasia BK, Neelu. IoT conceptual Model and Application,” *Internet of Things Frameworks for Enabling and Emerging Technologies*. 1st Edition, Ch 1, CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, USA 2022: 1-22.
20. Tiwari V, Chaurasia BK. Security Issues in Fog Computing using Vehicular Cloud. *International Conference on Information, Communication, Instrumentation and Control - (ICICIC-17)* 2017; 1-4 ; <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOMICON.2017.8279037>
21. Rai S, Chaurasia BK, Gupta R, Verma S. Blockchain-based NFT for Healthcare System. In *12th International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT)* 2023; 700-704. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNT57126.2023.10134632>
22. Calheiros RN, Ranjan R, Beloglazov A, De Rose CAF, Buyya R. CloudSim: A toolkit for modeling and simulation of cloud computing environments and evaluation of resource provisioning algorithms. *Softw. Pract. Exper.* 2011; 41(1): 23–50. <https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.995>

23.Cloudsim 5.0, Online available at: <https://www.javadoc.io/doc/org.cloudsimplus/cloudsim-plus/5.0.0/overview-summary.html>, Last accessed on 25 Feb., 2024.